

Towards a Framework for Intelligent Sampling: Comprehensive Review of Challenges, AI Techniques, and Tools

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Abstract—Intelligent data sampling is an innovative method that enhances conventional data sampling procedures by utilizing machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches. In this manuscript, we deep dive into the scientific and grey literature to find the main challenges faced by data sampling and elaborate on the various AI techniques utilized to mitigate them. We identify key issues such as class imbalance, overfitting, computational inefficiency, and bias, which often hinder traditional sampling methods. Furthermore, we explore AI-driven techniques that have been integrated into the sampling process to address these challenges effectively. As a result, we propose a novel framework for intelligent sampling that incorporates an AI-powered recommender system. This system dynamically selects the most appropriate sampling technique based on the specific characteristics of the data and the needs of the predictive model. By automating and optimizing the selection of sampling methods, our framework aims to enhance model performance, improve resource efficiency, and adapt to diverse real-world applications.

Index Terms—Intelligent Data Sampling, AI techniques, Framework, Challenges, Generative Adversarial Networks, Active Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Big Data encompasses vast volumes of information, posing significant challenges in terms of computational resources, storage, and processing efficiency. The complexity of analyzing such extensive datasets not only demands substantial infrastructure but also incurs considerable time costs before actionable insights can be derived [1]. Data sampling is a fundamental statistical technique that enables the selection, manipulation, and analysis of a representative subset of data in order to identify patterns and trends in a larger set of data [2]. In the field of data analysis and artificial intelligence, AI techniques have revolutionized the data collection process by raising the efficiency, accuracy, and capacity for handling large amounts of data [3]. Additionally, AI techniques can minimize the time spent on sample selection, enhance data representation, and maximize the identification of pertinent patterns [4]. This has led to increased accuracy in predictive

models and better understanding of trends across a variety of fields, from scientific research to market analysis [5].

A. Problem Statement

The DATAMITE [6] project faces a challenge with profiling large datasets that strain resources and take considerable time to analyze. A preliminary solution involved simplifying the dataset by using basic random sampling for analysis. However, the question arises: can the results from this reduced dataset be always considered representative of the original data? In the context of quality assurance and business-specific KPIs, the expertise of the analysis team becomes crucial. Therefore, it is important to understand how different sampling methods can impact the quality and relevance of the outcomes.

B. Contribution

Based on the aforementioned problem, the main contributions of this manuscript are:

- C1** A comprehensive analysis of artificial intelligence techniques applied to data sampling, systematically identifying the challenges.
- C2** The proposal of a framework to recommend the most suitable data sampling technique based on the specific characteristics of the scenario.

II. BACKGROUND

Since it is extremely difficult to learn a pattern or model from big data precisely and quickly [7], data sampling is a key technique for data analysis and machine learning used to select a representative subset of a larger dataset for further analysis [8]. In the context of big data analysis, traditional approaches such as data warehousing and SQL database management systems fall short for handling such tremendous volume and complexity [9]. Analogously, the authors in [8] identify the lack of representative sampling as critical in empirical software engineering and highlight that there is no single better technique, as their appropriateness is highly dependent on the purpose or circumstances. A similar concern

is shared in [10], where the authors propose a four-step method to create representative samples of software repositories. In the context of big data sampling, common techniques include Record-Level Sampling (RLS), as the random selection of individual records from the dataset, and Block-Level Sampling (BLS), as the random selection of blocks [9]. In [11], the authors discuss optimal subsampling methods to include logistic regression models, quartile regression models, and quasi-likelihood estimation and demonstrate their effectiveness to reduce the burden of dealing with massive datasets. Oversampling is a common technique used for imbalanced datasets. In [12], the authors address the challenge of imbalanced data, which is found in many real-world applications, and propose a method that improves the performance of state-of-the-art oversampling methods. Similarly, the authors in [13] propose an oversampling technique for imbalanced datasets that can improve balanced accuracy and F1-score of ML classification models.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To offer a thorough analysis of the different subtleties that exist at the nexus of artificial intelligence and data sampling, we have developed the following research questions, which are designed to address the problems identified in section I-A and will guide the discussion of this study.

- RQ1 What are the main challenges associated with using artificial intelligence for data sampling?
- RQ2 How are artificial intelligence techniques contributing to addressing challenges in data sampling?
- RQ3 What AI-based approaches and algorithms are used for data sampling?
- RQ4 What are the key frameworks, architectures, and technological platforms used in AI-driven data sampling?

IV. DISCUSSION

This section delves deeply into the scientific literature and offers a thorough synopsis of the key conclusions.

A. RQ1: What are the main challenges associated with using artificial intelligence for data sampling?

As data volume and complexity grow, traditional sampling methods struggle with large datasets. AI-driven sampling optimizes the process by selecting representative subsets that capture diverse patterns in the data. However, several challenges arise in this context. In [14], one of the most prominent issues is data imbalance, where ensuring a balanced dataset is crucial for accurate model training. Techniques like oversampling and undersampling are used, but they can still fail to maintain an ideal balance, potentially leading to biased or inaccurate models [15]. A further difficulty identified in [16] is the loss of essential information during sample size reduction. While sampling methods aim to preserve key data features, reducing the dataset may inadvertently exclude important information, resulting in less representative or overly simplistic models [17].

Additionally, biases in the original dataset may be amplified by AI sampling techniques [18]. In [19], AI-driven sampling methods have the potential to reinforce or even magnify biases, producing unfair forecasts, if they are not well controlled. Biased predictions can have serious repercussions in sensitive fields like healthcare or finance, thus this is especially important [20]. Another difficulty is the effect of slight changes in training data. AI models have trouble generalizing well to unseen data because even small sampling biases can have a big impact on model predictions. This problem emphasizes the necessity of robust methods and careful data selection to deal with these biases [18]. Besides, in [14], [21], ensuring a representative sample is crucial for AI models to generalize well. Sampling methods must capture the dataset's diversity, avoiding biases while preserving key trends [22].

In [21] data noise is another important problem. AI models may find it more difficult to identify precise patterns when noise is introduced by annotation or measurement errors. Using noise management techniques without sacrificing model performance is crucial. [20]. Many AI sampling algorithms struggle to maintain data quality while ensuring data diversity, risking over-fitting and disrupting important patterns [19]. Also, in [15] AI-driven sampling poses fairness concerns, and it is a major challenge to ensure models are unbiased while balancing accuracy and fairness.

Finally, ensuring model generalization on diverse data adds complexity, requiring AI sampling techniques to adapt to different distributions to maintain effectiveness. Balancing computational efficiency and adaptability is essential for practical deployment [17]. Moreover, the computational cost of AI-driven sampling techniques, such as active learning and reinforcement learning, remains a concern. These methods often demand significant resources, making scalability challenging, especially when handling large datasets or real-time applications [23].

B. RQ2: How are artificial intelligence techniques contributing to addressing challenges in data sampling?

As data volumes continue to grow, traditional sampling methods often struggle with efficiency, class imbalances, and data biases. Artificial Intelligence is solving these issues with sophisticated methods to enhance intelligent data sampling. Adaptive sampling methods based on AI facilitate the full handling of data by selecting and processing representative samples of massive datasets. For example, they reduced the processing time by 75%, while keeping the model accuracy, by employing adaptive sampling combined with a self-adaptive test suite module [24]. This substantially improves computational efficiency without sacrificing predictive performance.

AI is transforming medical imaging by adjusting training datasets to tackle class imbalances, such as under-segmentation and over-segmentation in brain MRI scans. By concentrating on minority classes, AI boosts the accuracy of abnormality detection, resulting in improved diagnostic outcomes [25]. AI systems can dynamically evaluate the significance of individual data samples, thus optimizing learning

efficiency. On top of that, AI-generated synthetic data helps balance datasets, reducing biases and enhancing fairness in AI models. By augmenting datasets with realistic synthetic samples, AI ensures more equitable decision-making processes [26], [27].

An importance-driven data collection approach outperforms conventional data collecting techniques by prioritizing data according to a model convergence measure, guaranteeing that the most useful information is included in training models [28]. Moreover, in [29], AI techniques like pseudo-labeling are essential for refining and improving the quality of annotated datasets. By adjusting and upscaling low-resolution data, these methods enhance model performance. Also, the combination of feature selection and data sampling proves to be crucial. In [30], data sampling application after feature selection tends to yield better and more accurate results, optimizing the overall process.

AI-powered algorithms optimize real-time data collection, improving both efficiency and accuracy. In [31], AI-driven nursing information collection system has demonstrated significant improvements in data acquisition, ensuring timely and precise patient information. Additionally, AI can work iteratively with human researchers to refine data collection processes. This collaboration allows AI to guide data collection toward areas of scientific significance, ensuring that datasets remain relevant and high-quality [32], thereby enhancing the effectiveness of AI models while leveraging human expertise.

C. RQ3: What AI-based approaches and algorithms are used for data sampling?

Artificial intelligence techniques play a crucial role in intelligent data sampling by obtaining better knowledge of the result's domain, enhancing the efficiency, accuracy, and representativeness of sampled datasets [33]. Active Learning (AL) iteratively selects the most informative data points for labeling, thereby maximizing model efficiency while reducing the number of required samples. This is particularly beneficial in industrial settings where data acquisition is expensive or limited [34]. In [35], surrogate modeling is presented as a technique for mixed adaptive sampling to optimize sample placement and reduce the required sample size. Methods such as Latin Hypercube Sampling [36], Gradient-Enhanced Sampling [37] and Monte Carlo Sampling [38] improve model efficiency by drastically lowering the number of samples needed and increasing model accuracy.

Over-sampling is a technique used in data processing to balance unbalanced datasets. One of the most popular methods is Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), which generates synthetic samples by interpolating between existing instances of the minority class, although it can introduce noise and outliers [39]. In [40], Adaptive Synthetic Sampling (ADASYN) prioritizes the generation of synthetic samples in areas where minority data are more difficult to learn, better adapting to the distribution of the data. In the same paper, K-Nearest Neighbor Oversampling (KNNOR), identifies critical and safe areas for synthetic data generation, considering the

compactness and location of the minority class relative to the others. In [12], the Selective Oversampling Approach (SOA) improves the performance of existing methods by identifying the most representative samples of the minority class using outlier detection techniques prior to oversampling. Furthermore, the combination of under-sampling and over-sampling uses techniques such as SMOTE to generate synthetic samples from the minority class, while removing redundant samples from the majority class, as with Tomek Links or ENN [41]. In [5], adaptive undersampling with reinforcement learning allows models to learn which samples to keep or remove based on classification performance, these methods can identify high-quality samples efficiently, even in large datasets. In [42], selective undersampling with deep learning balances datasets is used. Generating synthetic minority class data using models like ACVAE and then selectively removing noisy majority class samples with algorithms like ECDNN to enhance class separation.

In [43], the SVM model improves classification on unbalanced datasets by optimizing sample selection through techniques such as oversampling, facilitating the balanced representation of data and reducing classification errors to train more robust models. It also helps to identify and prioritize minority classes, improving accuracy and reducing bias. In [44], algorithms such as SCOTE LS-SVM demonstrate their effectiveness in these data sampling scenarios.

In [45], [46], the authors propose a Gan-Based Local Coordinate Coding (LCC) is introduced as a technique for sampling from a latent distribution learned from the data, preserving semantic information and improving the quality of generated samples with GAN models. In [47], Collaborative Sampling is proposed, where the discriminator guides the generator during sampling through gradient-based updates, shifting the generated samples closer to the real data distribution. Finally, in [48], Hierarchical Mixture of Generators is an approach in which multiple specialized generators cover different regions of the data, increasing both the diversity and quality of the generated samples. SOLUTIONS USING AI-DRIVEN DATA SAMPLING, ASSOCIATED AI TECHNIQUES, AND CHALLENGES SOLVED

D. RQ4: What are the key frameworks, architectures, and technological platforms used in AI-driven data sampling?

The methodologies that have been reviewed in section IV-C are being used in various big data solutions, as they solve some of the problems that in common big data applications appear. For example, in [49], active learning with a reliability sampling based framework has been developed, using heterogeneous radial basis function and neural networks acting as an active learner, valuable knowledge from unlabeled data is obtained. Also in this work, an initialization phase is performed using Latin hypercube sampling method, to calculate initial population, then an iteration process start, in which surrogate modeling, active learning to harness useful information, surrogate-assisted prediction and stochastic ranking-based selection is performed. On the other had, in [50] a

AI-Driven Data Sampling Solutions	Associated AI Techniques	Challenges Solved
ALeRSa-DDEA [49]	Active learning, surrogate modeling and latin hypercube sampling	Computational cost, representativeness and data imbalance
Multi-fidelity surrogate model (MFSM) [50]	Surrogate modeling and latin hypercube sampling	Representativeness, improve accuracy, computational cost and fairness
Hybrid SMOTE and DNN framework [51]	Synthetic minority oversampling	Data imbalance, generalization and ensuring quality
Prediction of ALC status tool [52]	Synthetic minority oversampling, class weights and random oversampling	Data imbalance and representativeness
Multimodal Pain Recognition tool [53]	Synthetic minority oversampling and K-Nearest Neighbor oversampling	Data imbalance, ensuring quality data and generalization
Cloud-Based Hybrid Intrusion Detection framework [54]	Adaptative synthetic sampling	Improve accuracy, data imbalance, noise in data and impact of small variations
Intrusion Detection System with CNN model [55]	Synthetic minority oversampling and K-Nearest Neighbor oversampling	Data imbalance, ensuring quality and generalization
Diagnosing the Disease of Diabetes tool [56]	Selective oversampling approach	Data imbalance, improve accuracy, bias reduction and representativeness
Addressing Imbalance in Health Data tool [42]	Selective undersampling and contrastive learning over sampling	Data imbalance, ensuring quality, improve accuracy and fairness
Anomaly Detection of Imbalanced Data Streams tool[57]	Generative adversarial network oversampling	Data imbalance, impact of small variations and representativeness
CTGAN-ENN [58]	Undersampling and GAN-based hybrid sampling	Data imbalance, class overlaps and generalization

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF THE SOLUTIONS THAT USE AI-DRIVEN DATA SAMPLING, THE ASSOCIATED AI TECHNIQUES, AND WHAT CHALLENGE THEY SOLVE

multi-fidelity surrogate model framework is proposed using non-hierarchical low-cost low-fidelity data, focusing on the relationship between low and high-cost fidelity data, building multiple bi-fidelity surrogate models, and using the weighted sum of all of them to build the multi-fidelity surrogate model.

SMOTE is a commonly used solution. For example, in [51], the combination of SMOTE and DNN is used to address the issue of insufficient data samples, leveraging the advantages of machine learning in environments that have a limited amount of data samples. In [52], random oversampling, class weights and SMOTE are used to solve the data imbalance that cause significantly underrepresented data classes. SMOTE was also used in [53] for data augmentation, and k-nearest neighbor was employed to make the predictions on the remaining unlabeled data, assessing pain in postoperative patients.

ADASYN has been used for a hybrid intrusion detection framework in [54], to address class imbalance problem via fine-tuning the class distribution with adaptive resampling. Another example of ADASYN implementation to tackle the class imbalance problem is [55], in which an intrusion detection system has been implemented for binary and multi-class classification. Also in this work, K-nearest neighbor has been used to identify created minority instances that are near decision boundaries.

Another type of proposal is [56], where stacking ensemble approach to diagnosis the disease of diabetes has been developed, using selective oversampling approach to extend the size of the minority class, balancing the data as much as possible. In [42], an oversampling technique trained with contrastive learning has been proposed, and in order to control

noise, selective undersampling has been used, filtering out the unrealistic samples, resulting in a more balance and informative dataset. GAN sampling solutions have gained relevance recently, with solutions like [57], in which a comprehensive anomaly detection framework with generative adversarial network oversampling has been used to overcome data streams imbalance. Another example is [58], where a framework with undersampling and GAN-based hybrid sampling was used to address the class overlap and imbalanced data problem in costumers data churn.

E. Summary

An overview of the solutions, techniques, and challenges previously covered in relation to AI-driven data sampling is given in Table I, for comprehending the state of intelligent data sampling. This summary makes it easier to recognize the many strategies employed to address the difficulties posed by data sampling, stressing both their benefits and possible drawbacks. Additionally, this synopsis establishes the baseline for the suggested framework in the following section, which suggests certain data sampling methods to improve data efficiency, representativeness, and quality across a range of applications. Moreover, it introduces an AI-driven recommendation system for data sampling based on specific challenges and requirements, ensuring the selection of the most suitable approaches for each scenario.

V. FRAMEWORK PROPOSAL

Figure 1 presents the data sampling framework workflow. The first step is the Data Sampling Recommender (1), which uses user input to define the dataset, output volume, and

Fig. 1. AI-Driven Data Sampling Workflow

metadata. Based on several factors, the recommender suggests the best sampling strategy. For balanced data, simple or stratified random sampling is recommended, while imbalanced data benefit from techniques like undersampling, oversampling, or SMOTE. For large datasets, random or systematic sampling maintains representativity, while for small datasets, preserving all information ensures integrity. Random sampling is suitable for uniform distributions, while stratified sampling is used for skewed distributions. If representativeness of subgroups is needed, stratified sampling is used, and for temporal patterns, systematic or cluster sampling is preferred. For resource-heavy models, undersampling is recommended, while SMOTE is used for synthetic data generation when computational power allows. Finally, oversampling or synthetic data generation is advised for models sensitive to data quantity, while less sensitive models can use mixed sampling techniques. These strategies ensure diverse, relevant data selection while minimizing bias and computational overhead.

The user schedules the sampling procedure after selecting a recommended technique, specifying the execution time, method, and destination path (2). Since data sampling is not instantaneous, an optimization mechanism enhances this process by analyzing system metrics—such as network traffic, CPU load, and storage availability—to determine the optimal execution window. Leveraging real-time analytics and historical patterns, the optimizer minimizes performance bottlenecks by scheduling tasks when resources are least constrained. Additionally, it can deploy sampling tasks closer to data sources, reducing data transfer overhead and ensuring seamless integration with ongoing operations. The chosen procedure is executed by the Data Sampling Process (3), extracting the necessary data sample and saving it in the specified destination directory. The procedure reduces biases and improves data integrity by using an organized strategy, which increases the sampled data reliability for further analysis.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The main challenges, cutting-edge artificial intelligence methods, and essential frameworks for optimizing data sampling, minimizing redundancies, and enhancing dataset representativeness have all been identified thanks to the literature review on intelligent data sampling. These results have led to the proposal of a framework that incorporates a recommender for data sampling techniques, which dynamically modifies the sampling method according to the data properties and system goals. As per the future work, the implementation and validation of this framework in real-world environments is proposed, evaluating its impact on data quality and the performance of data-driven systems. Additionally, optimization strategies will be explored to improve the adaptability of sampling in

scenarios with computational constraints or variability in data sources.

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